

A Retrospective Observational Clinicopathological Evaluation of Meningioma from Rural Setup

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of this study was to determine the incidence of Meningioma among all CNS tumors occurring in the study period, age and sex predilection, location, and site preference for a population in a rural setup of Bihar region.

Methods: This study was retrospective observational study at Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India for the period of 2 years. Out of 200 cases of CNS tumors operated, meningioma consists of 50 cases (25%). Ethical board permission was taken.

Results: The average age of presentation was 44.1 years. Most common affected age group was 30-50 years comprising 26 cases (52%). Out of 50 cases 42 (84%) were intracranial meningioma and 8 (16%) were spinal meningioma. The most common clinical symptoms for intracranial cases were headaches followed by seizures and vomiting. Among intracranial meningioma, the most common location was convexity meningioma (40%) followed by parasagittal (12%). Meningothelial meningioma 20 (40%) was the commonest subtype followed by transitional 12 (24%), psammomatous, 5 (10%), fibroblastic 2 (4%), metaplastic 1 (2%) and others. Grade II meningiomas included atypical 2 (4%), clear cell 1 (2%) whereas grade III included all the cases of papillary 1(2 %) and anaplastic 2 (4%) meningiomas.

Conclusion: The descriptive epidemiology of meningioma in our rural setup roughly correlates with the epidemiology elsewhere in India apart from the male to female ratio; which could be due to lack of seeking medical care among females in our society.

Keywords: CNS Tumor, Meningioma, Epidemiology of Meningioma.

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Introduction

Meningiomas are the most common primary central nervous system (CNS) tumors.¹ They are usually benign, slow growing neoplasms that are thought to arise from meningothelial (arachnoid) cells (MECs). [1-3] Despite having a reputation

of a benign disease, these dural-based tumors can lead to morbidity, presenting with a variety of non-specific, location dependent symptoms. MECs are a cellular component of the pia mater, arachnoid mater, and the trabeculae and septae of the

subarachnoidal space. [4] They make up a monolayer covering of the meninges and are connected via tight junctions, gap junctions, and desmosomes, providing an interface between neuronal tissue and the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). [5] Aside from providing a physical barrier to the CNS and protecting it from mechanical damage, MECs also play a significant role in immunological processes and the maintenance of homeostasis and host defense in the CSF. [6-8]

Cerebral convexities, sphenoid ridge, parasagittal, olfactory groove, tuberculum sellae and cerebellopontine angle are some of the favourite sites of intracranial meningioma. Spinal meningiomas occur more commonly in the thoracic region. Intraventricular and epidural meningiomas are rare. Pediatric meningiomas tend to occur at unusual locations, including the ventricles, posterior fossa and spinal dural regions. [9] Meningiomas are generally solitary, slowly growing tumours producing neurological signs and symptoms due to compression of surrounding structures; specific deficits depend upon the location of tumour. Imaging has an important role in characterizing these lesions and helping in presurgical differential diagnosis, which is essential for optimizing treatment strategies. The CT scan and MRI evaluate the lesion with respect to the following points: Location (supra/infratentorial) and site, periregional edema, intensity compared to grey matter, contrast enhancement and type of enhancement, presence of extra axial signs viz, CSF cleft, displaced subarachnoid vessels, buckling of cortical grey matter between the mass and the white matter, displaced and expanded subarachnoid space, broad dural base and bony reaction, presence of mass effect, presence of signal voids on T1WI and T2WI (calcification or fibrosis or vessels), presence of haemorrhage, heterogeneity, presence of necrosis or cystic change, presence of calcifications, margins: Sharp & well defined or ill-

defined On MRI, meningiomas are typically isodense, contrast-enhancing dural masses. "Dural tail" is a distinctive although non-specific feature of meningioma. Angiography often displays a characteristic tumour blush, reflecting their high vascularity. [10]

The aim of this study was to determine the incidence of Meningioma among all CNS tumors occurring in the study period, age and sex predilection, location, site preference for a population in a rural setup of Bihar region.

Materials and Methods

This study was retrospective observational at Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India for the period of 2 years. Out of 200 cases of CNS tumors operated, meningioma consists of 50 cases (25%). Ethical board permission was taken. Inclusion criteria consist of all the histopathological proven cases of meningioma. Rest of the CNS tumors was excluded from the study.

The details of the each patient were taken from medical records i.e. age, gender; clinical presentation, radiological evaluation (MRI and/or CT scan), location, brain infiltration and recurrence were noted. Intra operative consultation was done by squash smears for which sample was received in isotonic normal saline. Squash diagnosis was noted and was correlated with final histological diagnosis which was considered as gold standard for diagnosis of meningioma. The histological sections were viewed and all tumours were subtyped graded by experienced pathologist according to WHO 2007 criteria.

In all cases, the specimens received following surgery were fixed in 10% buffered neutral formalin for 24 hours. If the resected tissue was received as fragmented bits, all the tissues were submitted for processing. If the tumour was removed in toto and exceeded 4-5

cms, representative sections were taken. These tissue blocks were processed and embedded in paraffin wax. The paraffin embedded blocks were cut into 4-5 micron

sections and stained with routine Haematoxylin and Eosin stain (H&E).

Results

Table 1: Age and sex incidence of meningioma

Age	Male	Female	Total	%
<20	1	0	1	2
20-30	4	4	8	16
31-40	3	8	12	24
41-50	6	8	14	28
51-60	4	4	8	16
>60	4	3	7	14

The average age of presentation was 44.1 years. Most common affected age group was 30-50 years comprising 26 cases (52%).

Table 2: Types of meningioma and presenting complaints

Types of meningioma	N%
Intracranial meningioma	42 (84)
Spinal meningioma	8 (16)
Symptoms	
Headache	23
Seizure	15
Vomiting	8
Paresis	7
Visual Disturbance	5
Alt. Consciousness	4

Out of 50 cases 42 (84%) were intracranial meningioma and 8 (16%) were spinal meningioma. The most common clinical symptoms for intracranial cases were headache followed by seizures and vomiting.

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to location of meningioma

Location	N%
Convexity	20 (40)
Parasagittal	6 (12)
Sphenoid wing	4 (8)
Suprasellar	3 (6)
C.P angle	3 (6)
Others	14 (28)

Among intracranial meningioma, the most common location was convexity meningioma (40%) followed by parasagittal (12%).

Table 4: Histological sub-types of meningioma

Type	N%
Meningothelial	20 (40)
Transitional	12 (24)
Fibrous	2 (4)
Psammomatous	5 (10)

Microcystic	1 (2)
Secretory	1 (2)
Lipomatous& secretory	1 (2)
Metaplastic	1 (2)
Chordoid	1 (2)
Clear cell	1 (2)
Atypical	2 (4)
Papillary	1 (2)
Anaplastic	2 (4)

Meningothelial meningioma 20 (40%) was the commonest subtype followed by transitional 12 (24%), psammomatous, 5 (10%), fibroblastic 2 (4%), metaplastic 1 (2%) and others. Grade II meningiomas included atypical 2 (4%), clear cell 1 (2%) whereas grade III included all the cases of papillary 1(2 %) and anaplastic 2 (4%) meningiomas.

Discussion

In 1922, Harvey Cushing proposed the term meningioma [11] for the tumours arising from the arachnoid cells present in arachnoid villi and granulations and in stroma of perivascular spaces and choroid plexus. [12] Meningiomas constitute about 28–30% of primary Central Nervous System (CNS) tumours. They exhibit typical dural attachment and account for 15 % of intracranial tumours and about 25% of intraspinal tumours. [13]

Meningioma accounts for 33.8 percent of brain tumor. [14] In our study it consists of 25% of brain tumor similar to the studies by Ruberti RF et al [15] and AB shah et al.16 Most common affected age group was 30-50 years comprising 26 cases (52%) which was similar to the study by Ruberti R.F. [15] Spinal meningiomas comprised of 16% of total meningiomas in our study. In study done by Solero CL et al spinal meningiomas consist of 7.5-1 2.7% of all CNS meningiomas. Dorsal spine is reported as the most common location for spinal meningioma. [17-19]

Meningiomas are graded into Grade I, Grade II and Grade III with incidence in a ratio of 89%, 6%, 5% in this study. Nasrin

Samadi et al [20] reported as 86.1%, 8%, 5.9% while Konstantinos Violaris et al [21] as 89.82%, 5.82%, 4.36% for Grade I, Grade II and Grade III tumours respectively. MECs also protect against infection and neurodegeneration via phagocytosis of bacteria and apoptotic bodies, as well as macropinocytosis of neurotoxic peptides and proteins, respectively. [6-8] MECs have different embryologic origins depending on their anatomic locations. MECs found at the skull base and cerebral convexity have mesoderm and neural crest origins, respectively. This difference affects the predominating histological subtypes of meningiomas that arise from these cells and the distribution of recurrent somatic mutations. [22] Arachnoid cap cells make up the outer layer of the arachnoid mater and arachnoid villi and with cytological similarities to meningiomas cells, it is likely their cell of origin. [23] Meningiomas are tumors of the meninges but they also occur rarely as primary tumors in the ventricles of the CNS and extracranial organs such as the lungs, presumably from aberrant MECs. [24,25]

Conclusion

We conclude that most common histopathological variants of meningioma are meningothelial meningioma, followed by psammomatous meningioma. Most common WHO grade is grade 1. The most common age group for presentation of meningioma is third to fifth decade of life, and it is least common among children. It could be due to less reporting of female for medical care in rural setup. Meningiomas

are slow growing tumours arising from the meningotheial cells with a wide variety of histological patterns. These tumours are more common in women and Grade I tumours are predominant; Grade II and Grade III tumours are less frequent. Recurrence of tumours depends on histological grade and extent of surgery. Radiological localization helps in preoperative diagnosis while squash cytology is simple, cost effective and reasonably accurate method for intraoperative rapid diagnosis of meningioma.

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